

COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN WELDING JOINT METHODS OF CF/PP

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1. Introduction

In recent years, several measures for the better global environment have been taken in a variety of different fields. In a transportation sector, there are some measures for it and it is one of them to install lightweight materials to automotive body structures. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) can make an automotive structure lighter because of its high specific strength and specific stiffness [1].

CFRP can be classified into two categories by resins used. CFRTS (carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins) are becoming common lightweight materials for aircraft [2]. However, the productivity of CFRTS is not good to apply them to mass-produced automobiles, because curing of CFRTS is one of chemical changes and it takes a ten minute or more to cure [3]. On the other hand, the productivity of CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) is better than that of CFRTS, because it takes shorter to mold CFRTP components than CFRTS's, since this process uses coagulation reaction. Therefore the CFRTP are expected as materials for mass-produced automotive body structure [4]. In case of CFRTP, preforms of CFRTP are made by impregnating fibers previously with thermoplastics at material producers and the preforms are pressed into the shape of components one after another. It takes a few seconds to press a CFRTP component thanks to their thermal plasticity. However, large press machines are needed to mold CFRTP components because the viscosity of CFRTP's matrix is high [5]. Moreover it is difficult to press automotive body in one piece, because which is large and complex. Therefore a CFRTP automotive body is produced by assembling many

CFRTP components, which size is not larger than the size press machines can make.

Joining technologies are part of the key technologies to assemble. There are three types of joints for the CFRTP, mechanical joints, adhesive joints and welding joints. Mechanical joints and adhesive joints are also used to joint CFRTS components but welding joints are peculiar to CFRTP's joints because welding joints use their thermal plasticity. Welding joints are made in a way which a pair of CFRTP members is heating up at the joint surfaces until they melt and, after that, cooled down in a state where pressed against each other without any adhesives and fastenings. The joint surfaces are supposed to be integrated with the CFRTP members. In this paper, we consider two types of basic joint geometries, a single lap joint and a scarf joint [6]. A single lap joint is easy to make. However, when this joint bears the load in-plane, peel stress and stress concentration occur. On the other hand, a scarf joint is superior in joint strength due to no peel stress and no stress concentration. But it is more difficult to make a scarf joint than a single lap joint because joint surfaces need to be a tapered shape.

When we will use these welding joints, we will need to evaluate the joint strength. In these joints, the joint strength is defined by the joint shear strength. Therefore, we evaluated the joint shear strength in this paper. Moreover we also evaluated the interlaminar shear strength of the member and compared among three shear strengths; the joint shear strength, the interlaminar shear strength and the interfacial shear strength between the reinforcement and the matrix. This is because it is thought that there is a correlation between the joint

shear strength and the interlaminar shear strength, since the welding joint is made by overlapping members and the joint surface is supposed to be integrated with the members. And it is also thought that the interfacial shear strength affects the interlaminar shear strength, since the member is composed of fibers and resin and the interface is a one of the components of composites. Accordingly, we tried to unveil the relationship among these three shear strengths.

In order to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength and the joint shear strength, we conducted a double notch shear test and a tensile joint shear test in this paper.

2. Double notch shear test and Joint shear test

2.1. Materials

In this paper, we evaluated carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene (CF/PP), which is one of CFRTP. And this is a composite of carbon fiber and polypropylene. CF/PP is one of the promising CFRTP for mass-produced automotive bodies because the cost of the matrix is low and it is easy to handle since the melting point of the matrix is low and the viscosity is low. However, it was difficult to make a CF/PP because PP-homo, which is a basic polypropylene, is hard to cohere with carbon fiber [7]. Hence the PP modified chemically to improve the adhesion with carbon fiber have been developed in a part of Japanese METI-NEDO project, "Development of sustainable hyper composite materials technology [4][8]." We used three CF/PPs containing the developed PP as base materials for this research, which have also been developed in the project. We call these materials; uni-directional CF/PP (UD) plates, chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) plates and carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT) plates. The specifications of these are shown in Table 1. The UD and the CTT are made of the same material which is a prepreg tape composed of carbon fibers aligned in one direction and the developed PP. The UD plate is made by laminating the prepreg tapes in one direction. The CTT plate is made by stacking the chopped prepreg tapes in random directions, as shown in Figure 1. On the other hand, the CMT plate is made by impregnating a carbon fiber mat with the developed PP. The carbon fiber mat consists of respective fibers directing randomly.

All plates we used were molded in a hot plate press machine under the condition shown in Figure 2.

2.2. Double notch shear test

In order to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength of CF/PP plates, double notch shear test was conducted, according to ASTM D3846. The specimens for this test were cut down from the each base plate, as shown in Figure 3. In this test, the specimens were compressed longitudinally and the maximum load of each specimen was measured. Then we calculated the interlaminar shear strength τ_M of the each specimen. The τ_M means;

$$\tau_M = \frac{P_M}{bl} \quad (1)$$

where, P_M is a maximum load, b is a width of the specimen and l is the span length between the notches. The test results are shown in Figure 4. The bars in the graph show the mean τ_M of four specimens. An upper error bar shows the maximum value and lower one means the minimum value among four specimens.

After the tests, the failure surfaces were examined with SEM. The failure surface of the UD specimen is shown in Figure 5. Those of the CTT's and the CMT's are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The horizontal direction in these images is the longitudinal direction of the specimen.

2.3. Tensile test for welding joint

For fundamental examination of the welding joint shear strength, tensile tests on the single-lap joints and the scarf joints were conducted in this study. These joints on the specimens were made by a hot plate welding, as shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 and Table 2 show the specimen geometry and size for the joint test. Firstly the members were cut down from the each plate. Secondly a pair of the members was set with 12.5 mm or 25.0 mm lap in a mold for jointing. Lastly the mold was pressed in a hot press machine under the condition that is the same condition as molding the base plates. In case of scarf joint, before setting the members in the jointing mold, a pair of the members was milled tapered.

After preparation of specimens, an x-ray image of the joint was taken by computerized tomography (CT) scan. Figure 10 and Figure 11 shows the CT image of UD's each joint. Figure 12 and Figure 13

show the CT images of CMT's the single lap joint and the scarf joint. After taking images, tensile tests for joint shear strength were conducted. From the test result, the assumed joint shear strength τ_j^* was calculated. The τ_j^* means;

$$\tau_j^* = \frac{P_j}{bL} \quad (2)$$

where, P_j is a maximum load, b is a width of the specimens and L (12.5 mm or 25.0 mm) is a lap length respectively.

The test result of joint shear strength with 12.5 mm lap is shown in Figure 14 and that with 25.0 mm lap is shown in Figure 15. In these graphs, the bars show the average value of the joint shear strength and the error bars show the maximum value and the minimum value among 5 specimens.

Finally, we observed the failure surface of the joint by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Figure 16 shows the UD single lap joint the failure surface of the UD single lap joint. Figure 17 is a photo of the failure surface of the CTT single lap joint. There are some directional fiber tapes. Figure 18 is a close look of that. Figure 19 shows that of CMT single lap joint. The failure surface of scarf joint is shown in Figure 21, Figure 23 and Figure 22. They are UD's, CTT's and CMT's.

3. Discussions

3.1. Double notch shear test

The double notch shear tests were conducted to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength of the base materials. The relationship between interfacial shear strength between carbon fiber and matrix and interlaminar shear strength is shown in Figure 24. In this figure, the value of the UD plate with non-modified polypropylene is included as a reference [9]. The interfacial shear strength between the fiber and the polypropylene of the non-modified UD is 4.8 MPa and the interlaminar shear strength is 6.45 MPa.

Regarding the UD, there is a correlation between the interlaminar shear strength and the interfacial shear strength. As shown in Figure 5, the failure surface is broken at the interface between the fiber and the matrix but the matrix is not fractured.

Although the CTT is made from the same material of the UD, the interlaminar shear strength of the CTT is lower than that of the UD. This is because in

case of the UD all fiber directs longitudinally, however, in case of the CTT, the fibers on the failure surface direct randomly. This figure shows only one part of the failure surface, but it is clear that some fibers don't direct longitudinally and that there is a resin failure on the failure surface of the CTT specimen. This means there are some failure modes and they are mixed complex. Therefore it is difficult to find a relationship between the interlaminar shear strength and the interfacial shear strength because of the fibers stacking in a complex.

As to the CMT, the interlaminar shear strength is higher than the interfacial shear strength. We assume that the interlaminar shear strength is strengthened by tangling among the fibers.

The interlaminar shear strength of a composite which is reinforced in a longitudinal direction is affected by the interfacial shear strength between fibers and matrix. However there are the other factors that control the interlaminar shear strength of the composite which consist of fibers directing in random directions.

3.2. Joint shear strength

In order to evaluate the shear strength of the welding joint, we conducted the simple tensile test on the joint.

Figure 25 and Figure 26 show a relationship between the joint shear strength and the interlaminar shear strength of the base materials.

● UD

Regarding the single lap joint, we can find that there is no obvious joint surface in Figure 10. Therefore the joint is manufactured well and it is thought that the joint surface is integrated with the member.

Comparing Figure 14 and Figure 15, there is no difference between the lap lengths. The joint of this material may be affected a little by the shear lag.

The shear strength of the UD single lap joint has a relationship to the interlaminar shear strength of the UD. This is also found by comparing Figure 16 and Figure 11. The failure mode we can find in both images is the failure at the interface between the fibers and the matrix, due to the fibers are falling out from the matrix.

Addition to the result of the double notch shear test, there is a relationship among the interfacial shear strength between fiber and resin, the interlaminar

shear strength and the shear strength of the single lap joint.

As to the scarf joint, we can find the clear joint surface that is a resin layer in Figure 11. This means that the fibers are discontinuous at the joint surface.

The shear strength of the scarf joint is higher than that of the single lap joint. The one reason is the effect of the reduction of stress concentration thanks to the joint geometry.

The shear strength of scarf joint is supposed to be regardless of the lap length. However in this case, the shear strength of the specimen which lap length is 25.0 mm is stronger than 12.5 mm's. We can't understand why there is the difference of the scarf joint shear strength between the lap lengths and we need to make it clear.

- CTT

There are tensile failures of the resins where the composite is reinforced in the transverse direction of the specimen, as shown in Figure 18 and Figure 22. Joint surfaces of the CTT are reinforced in various directions, thus there are various failure modes in the joint failure surface of the CTT. This means that it is difficult to predict the joint shear strength of the CTT from the interfacial shear strength because there is many factors to define the joint shear strength.

The joint shear strength is stronger than the interlaminar shear strength. We estimate this is because of the evaluated size of the specimen. In case of the double notch shear test, the size, which is the area of 6.4 mm x 13.2 mm, is smaller than the size of the UD chopped tape. Thus there is a dominant fiber orientation in each layer and the interlaminar shear strength is determined by the shear strength at the weakest interlaminar. On the other hand, in case of the joint shear test, the evaluated size, which is 25.0 mm x 13.0 mm, is larger than the size of the chopped tape. Hence, the shear strength is determined by the average of the interlaminar shear strength at each point of the joint surface.

When a shear test of the CTT is conducted, the size of the specimen is important. It is necessary to use a large enough specimen in accordance with the size of the UD chopped tape.

- CMT

There is no difference between the shear strength of the single lap joint and that of scarf joint. There is no great geometrical difference between both joints.

The CT images of the welding joint (Figure 10 and Figure 11) show that the joint surface is well joined and is integrated with the members, since it is difficult to find the joint surface. However the joint specimens on conducting the tensile test break at the joint surfaces. Thus it becomes clear that the joint surface is not integrated with the members. This can also be seen from the fact the joint shear strength is weaker than the interlaminar shear strength of the CMT.

Figure 19 and Figure 23 show that fibers fall-out from the matrix. This means the joint shear strength is somehow affected by the interfacial shear strength. There are the other factors to determine the joint shear strength, for example the effect of the tangling fibers. Hence it is necessary to look closely at this material.

4. Conclusions

Regarding the UD, the interlaminar shear strength is almost same as the shear strength of the single lap joint (Figure 25). And these are also similar to the interfacial shear strength (Figure 24). From the images of the failure surface (Figure 5, Figure 16), the failure at the interface is dominant. Thus the interfacial shear strength affects the interlaminar shear strength and the shear strength of the single lap joint strongly.

In case of the CTT, it is difficult to find relationships of the interfacial shear strength with the interlaminar shear strength and the joint shear strength (Figure 24, Figure 25). The interfacial shear strength doesn't dominate the interlaminar shear strength and the joint shear strength. And, it is necessary to establish the appropriate specimen size depending on the size of the chopped tape when we conduct a test on this material.

As to the CMT, there is little difference between the shear strength of the single lap joint and the scarf joint. The interlaminar shear strength is much higher than the interfacial shear strength due to tangling fibers (Figure 24). On the other hand, the interlaminar shear strength differs from the joint shear strength (Figure 25, Figure 26).

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Table 1 Specifications of base plates

	UD	CTT	CMT
Carbon fiber	TR50S	TR50S	T700
Matrix	PP	PP	PP
Tensile Strength ⁱ	30.4 MPa	30.4 MPa	33.5 MPa
Shear Strength	23.4 MPa	23.4 MPa	26.3 MPa
Composite			
V_f	45%	45%	20%
Interfacial Shear Strength ⁱⁱⁱ	17.7 MPa	17.7 MPa	13.3 MPa

ⁱTensile Test [JIS K7161], ⁱⁱIosipescu Shear Test [ASTM D5379], ⁱⁱⁱFragmentation Test.

Figure 1 CTT plate and CMT plate

Figure 2 Molding conditions

Figure 3 Specimen for double notch test

Figure 4 Test result of double notch shear test

Figure 5 Failure surface of UD's after double notch test

Figure 6 Failure surface of CTT's after double notch test

Figure 7 Failure surface of CMT's after double notch test

Figure 8 Molds for welding joint

Single lap joint

Scarf joint

Figure 9 Specimen geometry for joint test

Table 2 Specimen size for joint test

	UD	CTT	CMT
L	12.5 mm 25.0 mm	25.0 mm	12.5 mm
b	13.0 mm	25.0 mm	25.0 mm
t	2.0 mm	2.0 mm	2.0 mm

Figure 10 CT image of UD's single lap joint

Figure 11 CT image of UD's scarf joint

Figure 12 CT image of CMT's single lap joint

Figure 13 CT image of CMT's scarf joint

Figure 14 Joint shear strength [lap length 12.5 mm]

Figure 15 Joint shear strength [lap length 25.0 mm]

Figure 16 SEM image of failure surface [UD Single lap joint: 25.0 mm]

Figure 17 Photo of failure surface [CTT Single joint: 25 mm]

Figure 18 SEM image of failure surface [CTT Single lap joint: 25.0 mm]

Figure 21 SEM image of failure surface [UD Scarf joint: 25.0 mm]

Figure 19 SEM image of failure surface [CMT Single lap joint: 12.5 mm]

Figure 22 SEM image of failure surface [CTT Scarf joint: 25.0 mm]

Figure 20 SEM image of failure surface [UD Scarf joint: 12.5 mm]

Figure 23 SEM image of failure surface [CMT Scarf joint: 12.5 mm]

Figure 24 Relationship between the interfacial and the interlaminar shear strength

Figure 26 Relationship between the interlaminar shear strength and the shear strength of the scarf joint

Figure 25 Relationship between the interlaminar shear strength and the shear strength of the single lap joint

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